

First DNA barcode and male genitalial studies of a dung beetle, *Heliocopris gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae) from Western Ghats of India

Pranil Jagdale¹, Sujata Magdum¹, Aparna Kalawate^{2*}, Swapnil Kajale³ and Yogesh Shouche³

¹ PG Department and Research Centre in Zoology, MVP Samaj's KRT Arts, BH Commerce & AM Science (KTHM) College, Nashik, Maharashtra-422002, India.

² Zoological Survey of India, Western Regional Centre, Vidya Nagar, Sector-29, P.C.N.T. (PO), Rawet Road, Akurdi, Pune, Maharashtra-411044, India.

³DBT-National Centre for Cell Science, Pune, Maharashtra-411007, India.

(Email: aparna_ent@yahoo.co.in)

Abstract

The present study reports the first DNA barcode for *Heliocopris gigas* (Linnaeus, 1748) from India. Also, the image of male genitalia along with its description is presented for the first time.

Keywords: Genitalia, first report, range extension, Maharashtra, coprophagous, Scarabaeinae.

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Introduction

The largest dung beetles in the world belong to the genus *Heliocopris* Hope, 1837 and are found in Africa, southern, and Southeast Asia (Tirant & René, 2017). There are 55 extant species of *Heliocopris* in the world (Schoolmeesters, 2023), and out of them, five are found in India: *H. bucephalus* (Fabricius, 1775); *H. dominus* Bates, 1868; *H. gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758); *H. midas* (Fabricius, 1775); and *H. tyrannus* (Thomson, 1858) (Mittal & Jain, 2015). The main source of food for these insects is the excrement of elephants, rhinos, and hippos. According to some reports, *H. gigas* has evolved to use the waste products of both domesticated and wild ruminants. Although, the article by Davis *et al.* (2008) suggests that these beetles moved from elephant dung to the dung of other herbivorous species, these insects were neither seen nor collected from beyond the Protected Areas. Previously, during our faunistic studies, the beetles from genus *Heliocopris* frequented the trap. However, the current fashion is for them to appear infrequently at the light trap. There are two beetles from this genus on the IUCN protected list: *Heliocopris faunus*

Boheman, 1857 and *Heliocopris japetus* (Klug, 1855). The first author encountered *H. gigas* during a recent survey. As a result, this research aims to offer the first Indian DNA barcode and male genital studies of *H. gigas*.

H. gigas shows sexual dimorphism like other species from this genus. The male beetles are black or brown with big horns or some outgrowth on their head and or thorax (Tirant & René, 2017). The horns are used for defense or to fight with the other males. The shape of horn is an important character for identification of the species. In the present study, male genitalia description along with images of adult and genitalia has been provided for the first time along with its first DNA Barcode from India.

DNA sequencing has been widely used in the ecological and phylogeny of coleopteran insects. One of the most often used markers is mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase subunit I (COI), which has a high mutation rate, fundamentally reliable primer binding region, and a large copy number per cell (Hebert *et al.*, 2003; Birky, 2007). Mt DNA barcode is used as an alternate approach for identifying insect

species and cataloguing new species to make it simple to identify morphologically cryptic species (Hebert *et al.*, 2003). Although there are several species of *Heliocopris*, as of right now, the genus has very limited genetic data. Thus, here in this study, the first mt DNA barcode for the species *H. gigas* from the Western Ghats of India is presented.

Materials and Methods

a. Sampling of dung beetles

Specimen for the present study was collected at night using a light trap. The map of the collection locality was prepared using open free QGIS software. The details of the collection locality are given under material examined and also shown in Fig. 1. For morphological analysis the specimen was studied under Leica EZ4E stereomicroscope with inbuilt camera. The images of adult were captured using Olympus Tough TG-6 Optical Zoom Camera.

The identification was carried out using literature (Arrow, 1917; Tirant & René, 2017). Further, the voucher specimen was deposited in National Zoological Collection of Zoological Survey of India, Pune, Maharashtra (India).

b. DNA isolation, amplification and Sequencing

The ethanol preserved tissue was used for DNA isolation. DNA from the tissues of the beetle was extracted from leg using DNeasy kit (Qiagen), according to the manufacturer's instructions. The obtained DNA was amplified using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using ABI thermocycler. Following primers (Meyer *et al.* 2005) were used for amplification of COI gene:
dgLCO F1
5'GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGAYATYGG 3'
and dgHCO R1
5'TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAARAAAYCA 3'. PCR reaction was carried out in total volume of 25 µl containing 2 µl DNA template, 10 pmol of each primer and 2 µl of dNTP and 0.2 µl of Taq polymerase (Banglore GeNei). Thermo-cycling conditions were as follows:

One initial cycle of 1 min at 95°C followed by five cycles of 95°C for 1 min, then denaturation 35 cycles of 95°C for 1 min, annealing at 52°C for 40 s, extension at 72°C for 1 min 15 s and final extension of 72°C for 5 min.

From each PCR reaction, 2 µL of the PCR product was visualized on a 2% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide, together with a GeneRuler 100 bp Plus DNA Ladder (Thermo Scientific). The obtained PCR products were sequenced with both, the forward and reverse, primers using an automated sequencer (3730 DNA analyzer, ABI, Hitachi).

c. Data analysis

Sequences were edited to remove ambiguous base calls and the forward and the reverse sequences were assembled using Chromas Pro version 1.34 (Technelysium Pty Ltd., Tewantin, Queensland, Australia). FASTA format of *H. gigas* sequences was used for BLAST search at NCBI. All the obtained sequences were aligned and manually edited using BioEdit version 7.2.6. The Maximum Likelihood method and Tamura 3-parameter model (T92) model of base substitution was used to calculate pairwise genetic distance in MEGA X version 10.0.5. Additionally, the sequences available in the GenBank for *Heliocopris* were downloaded (Table 1) to construct a phylogenetic tree. To avoid use of sequences from wrongly identified species, only sequences which formed monophyletic clades with the sequences studied here were selected. These sequences along with our data were used to generate ML trees using MEGA X (Nei and Kumar, 2000; Kumar *et al.*, 2018) treating *Onitis subopacus* Arrow, 1931 as outgroup (Fig. 2).

Results and Discussion

Morphologically the collected sample was identified as *Heliocopris gigas* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 3).

Systematic account

Order: Coleoptera Linnaeus, 1758

Suborder: Polyphaga Emery, 1886

Super family: Scarabaeoidea Latreille, 1802

Family: Scarabaeidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily: Scarabaeinae Latreille, 1802

Genus: *Heliocopris* Hope, 1837

Heliocopris gigas (Linnaeus, 1758)

1764. *Scarabaeus gigas* Linnaeus, *Mus. Lud. Uir.*: 16.

1928. *Heliocopris gigas* Arrow, *Trans. Ent. Soc. Lond.* : 74, pl. 5., figs. a & 4.

Figure 1. Collection locality of *H. gigas* from the Western Ghats, Maharashtra, India.

Figure 2. Maximum likelihood (ML) tree for the species of *Heliocopris gigas* based on the mitochondrial COI DNA gene sequences.

Table 1. Details for the mt DNA COI sequences utilized in the construction of the phylogenetic tree

Sr. No.	GenBank Accession No.	Locality	Species name as per NCBI	Publication details as per NCBI
1	MT169780.1	Pakistan	<i>Heliocopris bucephalus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Unpublished
2	MN344865.1	USA	<i>Heliocopris haroldi</i> (Kolbe, 1893)	Unpublished
3	AY131879.1	UK	<i>Heliocopris hamadryas</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Unpublished
4	AY131878.1	UK	<i>Heliocopris andersoni</i> (Bates, 1868)	Unpublished
5	AF499751.1	South Africa	<i>Heliocopris hamadryas</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Unpublished
6	MG188320.1	India	<i>Heliocopris gigas</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Current Study

Figure. 3A-E. *Heliocopris gigas*: **A.** Dorsal view; **B.** Lateral view of head; **C.** Pronotum; **D-E.** Male genitalia: **D.** lateral view; **E.** dorsal view.

Material examined: 01 male, Trimbakeshwar, Nashik district (19.9305, 73.5248), 24.xii.2020. coll. Pranil Jagdale (ZSI-WRC-ENT-1/2842).

Description: (Fig. 3A-C) Male, Length (from tip of head to tip of abdomen): 38 mm; maximum width: 24 mm. Black, with a deep reddish-black lower surface and elytra; covered

in reddish hair on the sides of the head, sides and anterior part of the pronotum, legs, and mouth organs. The upper surface is closely rugose and not shining. The clypeus depressed, with two little prominences on each side of its edge. The pronotum is narrow and short, with a steep anterior declivity that bears noticeable reddish hairs and a prominent posterior portion in the

middle. The surface is rough and irregularly rugose, with a smooth region on each side. The lateral horns on head are short, and a transverse carina, occasionally bidentate. The dorsal horn of the thorax short with reduced lateral processes.

Male genitalia (Fig. 3D-E): Extremely sclerotized. Parameres slightly larger than the phallobase, broad and tip blunt.

Distribution: India: (Bihar, Chandigarh, Gujarat, Haryana, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Punjab, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal). *Elsewhere:* Egypt, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somalia, Sudan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Oman, Qatar, Iran (Arrow, 1917; Mittal & Jain, 2015; Kalawate, 2018; Schoolmeesters, 2023).

DNA Barcode diagnosis

The sequence of COI gene was isolated from the adult male. No matches were found among the already-existing entries in the GenBank's database after analysis with the BLAST. The preliminary molecular analysis was carried out for genus *Heliocopris* using available data from NCBI GenBank (Table 1). The evolutionary history was inferred by using the Maximum Likelihood method and Tamura 3-parameter model (Tamura, 1992). As expected, phylogenetic position of *H. gigas* was within species of genus *Heliocopris* with outgroup of *Onitis subopacus* Arrow, 1931 from same tribe.

The species of *Heliocopris* are true dung beetles feeding mainly on elephant dung. The *Heliocopris* beetles are tunnelers and can be observed under the tunnels dug by them. Thus, increases the soil texture and aeration. Due to the feeding habit of these beetles on dung, the dipteran flies, which are parasites on animals also gets controlled naturally. Interestingly, the South African Forest Department has acknowledged their significance and has placed traffic signs in the National Park that reads, "Do not drive over dung beetles or elephant dung" (Tirant & René, 2017). To raise awareness about the function of dung beetles and other insects in the environment, the Forest Department officials in India may install the same signage in the restricted forest.

In an attempt to develop the barcode data of the coleopteran insects, the specimen of *H. gigas* was used to generate the DNA barcode of this species from India. The present mt DNA Barcode data generated is expected to be helpful in building a reliable DNA barcode library for the country with a voucher specimen. The current study presents the first DNA barcode of *H. gigas* from India along with the male genitalial image and description.

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